

Biamperometric Determination of Sulfhydryl Groups at Low Concentrations Using Mercury Pool Electrodes

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The biamperometric titration for the determination of -SH groups with mercuric chloride in various compounds at stationary mercury pool electrode has been carried out in a faintly acidic medium ($pH \sim 4.6-5.6$) and faintly alkaline medium ($pH \sim 7.2$). The compounds estimated are cysteine hydrochloride, β -mercaptopropionic acid, toluene 3:4 dithiol, glutathione, 2-mercapto-5-anilino 1,3,4 thiodiazole, 3-mercapto-4-phenyl-5-anilino 1, 2, 4 triazole, *o*-mercapto benzoic acid, thioglycolic acid, thiomalic acid, 2-mercapto ethanol thiophenol and 2-mercapto benzothiazole. The error was observed to be within 2%.

THE present investigation was undertaken with a view to study the estimation of -SH groups in faintly acidic medium ($pH \sim 4.6-5.6$) and faintly alkaline medium ($pH \sim 7.2$) using two stationary mercury pool electrodes at constant applied voltage. Several compounds of biological¹⁻³ interest were estimated at low concentrations.

Experimental

All chemicals were obtained commercially. Sulphur contents of these compounds were estimated and ascertained by Carious method⁴. Stock solution (0.05M) of mercuric chloride was prepared by dissolving accurately weighed quantity of A.R. mercuric chloride in conductivity water. Dilute solution of $HgCl_2$ were obtained by appropriate dilution. Compounds to be investigated were prepared daily and kept under nitrogen. Experimental set up was similar to that described by Stone and Scholten⁵.

End points were determined graphically by the plot of the current against volume of the titrant added. The titration curve has usually reverse L shape. A typical titration curve is shown in Figure 1. Results of the investigations are recorded in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The substances involved in the titration are soluble in some cases on addition of modest quantity of alcohol. The reaction takes place on addition of the titrant, thus forming an irreversible couple and the current through the titration cell is low and remains almost constant and a rapid increase in the current indicates the end point (Fig. 1). The specificity of the method for -SH groups is of a high order due to high sensitivity of the mercury pool electrode which

TABLE I. DETERMINATION OF -SH GROUPS. VOLUME OF THE TITRATION MIXTURE 30 ml. CONCENTRATION OF MERCURIC CHLORIDE SOLUTION $10^{-3}M$.

No.	Compound	Applied voltage mv	Buffer	pH	Amount taken mg	Average relative error%
1	Cysteine hydrochloride	25	acetate	4.6-5.6	0.1563 to 1.5635	-1.23
2	β -mercapto propionic acid	"	"	"	0.0132 to 0.2119	-1.32
3	Toluene 3 : 4 dithiol	"	"	"	0.0311 to 0.3122	+0.13
4	Glutathione (reduced)	"	"	"	0.0469 to 1.5640	+0.73
5	2-mercapto-5-anilino-1,3,4-thiodiazole	"	"	"	0.0842 to 0.4214	-0.46
6	3-mercapto-4-phenyl 5-anilino-1,2,4-triazole	"	"	"	0.0268 to 0.5362	-0.59
7	<i>o</i> -mercaptobenzoic acid	"	"	"	0.0386 to 0.3089	+0.23
8	Thioglycolic acid	50	"	"	0.3722 to 1.3959	+0.15
9	Thiomalic acid	25	Phosphate	7.2	0.0310 to 0.3101	-0.18
10	2-mercapto ethanol	etc.	etc.	"	0.0146 to 0.0293	-1.03
11	Thiophenol	"	phosphate (alcoholic)	"	0.0408 to 0.2044	-0.20
12	2-mercapto benzothiazole	100	"	"	0.3392 to 0.8484	+0.47

exhibits no difficulty related to conditioning of surface.

At this low voltage the error in case of thioglycolic acid, thiophenol and 2-mercapto-benzothiazole was observed to be considerably high (not reported) and so the titration was carried at 50 mV and 100 mV applied voltage. The results obtained were within experimental error.

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FIG. 1. TITRATION OF 0.0625 mg. GLUTATHIONE WITH M.P.E. AT 25 mV.

From Table I it is evident that for each Hg^{+2} ion two sulfhydryl (-SH) group are required for the reaction, thus the end point in the titration of sulfhydryl group at the mercury pool electrode corresponds to the ratio of 1 HgCl_2 to 2-SH.